

REPORTED CASES IPC CRIMES AGAINST CHILDREN IN WEST BENGAL, INDIA: A STUDY WITH RECENT DATA

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Article History:

Received: 5- Jan -2022

Revised: 20 Mar- 2022

Accepted: 18- May-2022

First Published:30-Jun-2022

Cite This Article as:

Banerjee S, Biswas C.S, Pal M, Biswas

S, Hossain M.G & Bharti P. "Reported Cases IPC Crimes Against Children In West Bengal, India: A Study With Recent Data", International Journal of Social Sciences & Economic Environment, Vol. 7 Issue 1, 2022 pp 27-40

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.53882/IJSSEE.2022.0701004>

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The Journal follows the Best Practice guidelines and this statement is based on the guidelines and standards developed by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE). <https://publicationethics.org/>

ABSTRACT

Objective of the study: The present study tries to explore the variation in criminal cases of crimes against children in West Bengal vis-à-vis India during the period 2006 to 2017.

Methodology: This is mainly a descriptive study, which uses secondary information collected from the official records of the National Crime Records Bureau from 2006-2017 of India and West Bengal. The present study considers only the crimes against children that are punishable under IPC. Linear regression is carried out to explore the crime against children which is increasing over the years.

Findings: The data shows that all sorts of crime against children are increasing over time and that more than 90 percent of crimes against children are committed by known people.

Implications: There should be awareness programmes by the Government of India and the respective State Governments to teach the parents and the teachers of schools about how to prepare the children against any move committed against them and how to treat the children if such mis-happenings are already committed. The NGOs and mass medias also have their specific roles in order to stem violence against children.

Limitations: Firstly, the study was based on secondary data. Hence, sometimes it was not specific to researcher's needs. Secondly, National Crime Records Bureau provides history of crime upto 2017 and afterwards no further records regarding crimes were updated. So, the present situation of overall crime against children in India was not known.

Key words Kidnapping, Murder, Rape, Trafficking of girls

INTRODUCTION

Child abuse is a century old problem in India, and it has been a major social concern. Children have been brought, sold, enslaved, killed, physically abused (Paranjape, 2005). Children experience different forms of violence within and across the cultures. According to (World Health Organization, 1999.) defines "child abuse or maltreatment is an all forms of physical and emotional ill-treatment,

sexual abuse, neglect or negligent treatment or commercial or other exploitation, resulting in actual or potential harm to a child's health, survival, development or dignity in the context of a relationship of responsibility, trust, or power".

Children provide eternal optimism in the human being and provide potential for the development of nation. Every developing and developed nation links its future with the status of the child. A child of today cannot develop to be a responsible and productive member of tomorrow's society unless an environment, which is conducive to his social and physical health is assured to him. Neglected children mean loss to society as a whole. If the child is deprived of their childhood socially, economically, physically, and mentally then the nation gets deprived to potential human resources for social progress, economic empowerment, peace and order etc (Siddique and Parveem, 2021). UNICEF (2014) revealed that effects of violence in early childhood may be difficult to reverse and can have negative impact on children's future productivity and ability to form a relationship. The impact of violence or crime against children can be lifelong and even passed from generation to generation. Study of Finkelhore et al, (2009), revealed that when young people becomes victim of violence, the likelihood of their becoming future victims and of acting violently themselves as adults increases. Victim can become perpetrator. The Study of Pinheiro (2006) revealed that violence can trace negative impact on children's educational performance and achievement which can have long term economic consequences including poverty. Exposure to violence at an early stage can impair brain development and have mental problems. Violence can lead acute and long term problems for children's physical, sexual and reproductive health as well as their psychological well – being (UNICEF, 2014).

According to NCRB (2017), more than 40,000 crimes were committed by juveniles in 2019. Study revoked that 72 percent of the juveniles are aged between 16-18. Rate of crime by juvenile increases at an alarming rate in India, parliament has enacted the Juvenile Act 2015 where the juvenile will be treated as adult if they accused of committing heinous offences.

The hypothesis of the present study is that does crime against children is increasing at an alarming rate? The study also tries to reveal who is the perpetrator for crime against children, Generally perpetrator were known to children most of the time.

The present study tries to explore the variations in the crimes committed against children in West Bengal from 2006 to 2017. This study tries to depict the trend in the number of murders, rape, kidnapping and abducting, trafficking of minor girls for prostitution and other crimes during this period. Variation in crime against children in India (combined crime against children in all the states) was also shown to understand the grave situation of West Bengal compared to the Indian overall situation.

Violence prevention needs to start from childhood and should continue to later life. The present study will help to break the chain of violence that starts in childhood. Every child should

be taught to show zero tolerance to violence. The present study will initiates policy. Policy making is essential to long lasting social change. Many initiatives taken by the Indian Government towards creating a protective environment fir children as per law such as Juvenile Justice (Care and protection)Act 2000; the children 1098 service in partnership with Integrated Program for street children, signing and ratification of the United Nations Convention on the rights of the child (UNCRC), and Ratification of the Optional Protocols, The National Plan of Action, 2005, The National Policy for Children, 1974, Study on Child Abuse 2007. Many cases have been filed under the recent Protection of Children Against Sexual Offences Act (2012) and Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, which have successfully translated in increased convictions, demonstrating how legislating can curb child trafficking.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

During this period, Variation in crime against children in India (combined crime against children in all the states) was also shown to understand the grave situation of West Bengal compared to the Indian overall situation Serious attention started to be paid to the issue of child abuse and neglect as the physician and researcher C. Henry Kempe called for awareness programme about 50 years back regarding child sexual abuse as a serious medical, developmental, and social problems (Joshi 2018: 100-106).

Each year, millions of children around the world become victims of crime and witness physical, sexual, and emotional violence. Violence against children is a global problem, with a serious impact on the victim's physical and mental, well-being and development throughout their lives (Leung, Won, Chen and Tang 2008: 1-27). Approximately 150 million female children and 73 million male children under 18 have experienced forced sexual intercourse or other forms of sexual violence in 2002 (WHO, 2006). Approximately 40 million children are exposed to abuse each year, (WHO, 2016).

In India, as in many other countries, there has been no understanding of the extent, the vastness, and modes of the problem regarding crimes against children. According to the National Family Health Survey, 2015-2016 published in (2017), 30 percent of women below 15 years of age have reported that they have experienced physical violence and about 6 percent have experienced sexual violence in their lifetime. The Times of India, (Bhopal edition 2012, 24 November 2012) reported that one in every two children is suffering from child sexual abuse in India, while 80 percent of the cases are unreported. Many studies have been carried out on the criminal cases against children (Chatterjee, Chakraborty, Srivastava and Deb 2006: 167-182; Manikandan 2013: 62-68; Sahay 2010: 343-364). Finkelhor (1994) revealed that many sexual abuse of child remains undisclosed. Many researchers have concluded that the best picture of the scope of the problem is obtained by asking questions from adults about their childhood experiences.

The present study tries to explore the variations in the crimes committed against children in West Bengal from 2006 to 2017. This study tries to depict the trend in the number of murders, rape, kidnapping and abducting, trafficking of minor girls for prostitution and other crimes.

METHODS

Secondary information from the official records of National Crime Records Bureau from 2006-2017 of India and West Bengal are obtained to carry out the present study. It considers only the recorded cases committed against children. In this study, following the Juvenile Justice Act 2000, below 18-year-old individuals are considered as children. This study focuses on crimes against children in West Bengal. To get a better understanding of the crime against children situation in West Bengal, data on all India level crimes against children are also presented here. It is a cross-sectional, comparative as well as ex-post-facto research. The crime against children can be categorized into two groups: Crimes committed against children that are punishable under Indian Penal Code (IPC) and Crimes committed against children that are punishable under Special and Local Laws (SLL). The present study considers only those crimes against children that are punishable under IPC. The crimes against children covered in this study are murder, rape, kidnapping and abducting, procurement of minor girls and selling for prostitution. The crimes like infanticide, feticide, abetment to suicide, exposure and abandonment, child marriage, buying of girls for prostitution are merged and termed as other crimes, since rate of these crimes are either rare or absent in West Bengal. Many new crimes that appeared in the report after 2014 are excluded from the study to keep parity in the variables for showing the trend.

Linear regression model was used to find trends in crime over time. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant in the analysis. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (IBM Version 21).

Results

Table 1 shows crime against children in India and West Bengal from 2006- 2017. It was observed that the number of crime in India have been increasing over time, while the number of crime in West Bengal sharply increasing from 2010.

Table 1: Crime against children in India and West Bengal from 2006- 2017

Year Number of crimes in India % variation Number of cases in West Bengal % variation

Year	Number of crimes in India	% variation	Number of cases in West Bengal	% variation
2006	16691		432	
2007	18291	9.58	361	-16.43
2008	20486	12.0	513	42.10
2009	21216	3.56	484	-5.65

2010	22923	8.04	880	81.81
2011	28668	25.06	1450	64.77
2012	33538	16.98	1706	17.65
2013	50683	51.12	2530	48.30
2014	46110	-9.02	3536	39.76
2015	58953	27.85	3379	-4.44
2016	54741	-7.14	4391	29.94
2017	86344	57.73	4310	-1.84

Source: NCRB; negative percentage means a decrease in percentage compared to previous year

Figure 1(a-c) shows that the number of crimes committed against children in India is increasing over the years. During the period of 2006 to 2010 increase in crimes against children is relatively slow compared to that of the year 2011 to 2017. There is a sharp rise in crime against children from the Year 2011 and onwards, except for the period 2014 to 2016. The maximum percentage increase of crimes against children in India can be observed in the year 2017, whereas in the year 2014 and 2016 the percentage of crime has decreased. West Bengal witnesses the highest rate of crimes against children in the year 2010, whereas in 2007, 2009, 2015 and 2017 the crime against children has decreased compared to the previous year. This table also shows that a total of 86344 cases of crimes against children are registered in India during 2017 as compared to 16691 cases during 2006 and in West Bengal, 4310 cases in the year 2017 against 432 cases of crime children in 2006. The result implies that over the years (2006-2017) crime against children in India increased nearly 5 times, whereas in the West Bengal crime cases increased nearly 10 times (Fog. 1(a), Fig. 1(b), Fig. 1(c)).

Fig. 1(a): Number of Crime Cases in West Bengal: 2006-17

Fig. 1(b): Number of Crime Cases in India: 2006-17

Fig. 1(c): Number of Crime Cases in West Bengal and India: 2006-17

Table 2 and Fig 2 depicts that most types of crime cases have increased over the years. Murder cases have increased from 03 in 2006 to 60 in 2017, 20 times increase in 11 years. The percentage share of West Bengal in all India's murder cases also increased from 0.23 percent to 4.42 percent during this time. The number of rapes also increased until 2013; there are no rape

cases for next two years. But it is observed that in the year 2016, there is a massive increase in rape cases over the previous years in West Bengal. Kidnapping and abducting is increasing over the years, (except in the years 2007, 2015 and 2017). During 2006 to 2017, the number of cases regarding kidnapping and abducting has increased nearly by 22 times as well as the percentage share in India (4% in 2006 to 7% in 2017). Nearly one third of all the procurement of minor girl cases in India is from West Bengal. The cases of selling girls for prostitution decreased over the years (2006-2017). In 2006 the number of cases of selling girls for prostitution is 114, which decreases to 38 in 2017. In 2006, West Bengal contributed 92.68 percent of all cases of selling girls for prostitution in India. By the year 2017, the percentage share of West Bengal in all India cases of selling girls for prostitution decreased to 47 percent as shown in table 2. Other crimes in West Bengal also increased during this time period (nearly 8 times). The total crimes from 2006 to 2017 against children in West Bengal increases nearly 10 times (Fig.2).

Table 2: Total number of crimes against children registered in West Bengal 2006-2017

Year	Number of crimes in West Bengal						Total
	Murder	Rape	Kidnapping and abducting	Procurement of minor girls	Selling of girls for prostitution	Other crimes	
2006	03	20	156	77	114	62	432
2007	12	92	88	54	55	60	361
2008	18	129	196	53	41	76	513
2009	20	109	199	41	49	66	484
2010	16	73	332	200	115	144	880
2011	46	252	660	298	87	107	1450
2012	45	285	767	369	56	184	1706
2013	68	377	1388	486	69	142	2530
2014	64	0	2351	852	67	202	3536
2015	53	0	1951	1003	91	281	3379
2016	67	718	4178	706	67	1519	4391
2017	60	0	3516	216	38	505	4310
Number of crimes in India							
2006	1258	4248	3917	230	123	1281	10947
2007	1315	4630	5161	253	69	1257	12685
2008	1251	5120	6369	224	49	1198	14211

2009	1411	5024	6641	236	55	1082	14449
2010	1377	5142	7637	679	126	1068	16029
2011	1407	6742	11688	859	111	1012	21819
2012	1555	8087	14487	806	104	1351	26390
2013	1621	11549	22130	1224	06	1606	38136
2014	1767	12704	12126	2020	14	1511	30142
2015	1699	9858	34780	3080	105	1389	50911
2016	1601	18862	48582	2464	120	1365	72994
2017	1357	10011	29221	3382	81	1675	45727

Source NCRB

Fig. 2: Total number of crimes against children registered in West Bengal 2006-2017

Table 3 shows the crime against children from 2006-2017 using the linear regression model. Here, dependent variable includes: Murder, rape, kidnapping and abducting, procurement of minor girls, selling of girls for prostitution and other crimes; Independent variable: years. The study revealed that a significant increase in murder cases against children can be observed with the advancement of years. If the year increased 1 unit, then murder cases also increase by 6.09 and 31.112 respectively in West Bengal and India. The result shows that rape cases also increase by 17.171 respectively in West Bengal, though no significant association found with respect to the increase of years (1 unit). But in India, a significant increase in rape cases was found with respect to an increase of years. The present study depicts that with an expected increase in each year, a crime against children like kidnapping abducting, and procurement of minor girls shows progress by 349.965 and 66.542 respectively in West Bengal whereas in India 4207.164 and 297.577 respectively. The selling of girls for prostitution shows a decrease in number with the advancement of the year by 1.598 in West Bengal. No significant result was found. In the case of India, the selling girls for prostitution increases by 1.675 respectively but the result is not

significant. Other crimes in West Bengal and in India increases by 70.594 and 421.101 respectively and the result is significant at 5 percent level with respect to advancement of years (Fig. 3, Fig.4, Fig.5).

Table 3: Crime against children from 2006 to 2017 in West Bengal and India using linear regression model

West Bengal				India		
Dependent variable	B	95.0% C.I		B	95.0% C.I	
		Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
Murder	6.091**	4.208	7.974	31.112*	5.501	56.723
Constant	-12212.530			-61064.396		
Rape	17.171	-22.399	56.742	1024.860**	497.326	1552.394
Constant	-34368.878			1024.860		
Kidnapping abducting	349.965**	231.353	468.577	4207.164**	2911.980	5502.349
Constant	107079.258			-8440220.311		
Procuration of minor girls	66.542**	21.753	111.331	297.577**	212.385	382.769
Constant	-133486.232			-597286.564		
Selling of girls for prostitution	-1.598	-6.551	13247.123	1.675	-3.499	6.848
Constant	3284.930			-3273.494		
Others crime	70.594*	7.706	133.483	421.101*	93.575	748.628
Constant	-141721.647			-838939.880		

Source NCRB

Fig. 3: Age profile of victims of POCSO-2017 in West Bengal

Fig. 4: Age profile of victims of POCSO-2017 in India

Table 4 depicts that in the majority of cases crime was reported against girls. The age group 6 and 16-18 years boys in West Bengal have no registered crime cases. More than 95 percent of crimes have been committed against girls in West Bengal and India. This proves that girls are more vulnerable than boys both in West Bengal as well as in India. The study reveals that as the age increases crime cases against girl’s increases in West Bengal and India. Only a few cases are recorded as crimes committed against boys in both West Bengal and India. Whereas crime cases against girls are much in number which is very shameful for our society. The result also indicates that in Indian society children are the most vulnerable and innocent victims of crime especially girls as shown in Fig 3 and 4.

Table 4: Age profile of victims of POCSO-2017

Fig. 4: Age profile of victims of POCSO-2017 in India

Fig.5: Offenders relation to child victims of POCSO (Section 4 and 6)-2017

Table 4 depicts that in the majority of cases crime was reported against girls. The age group 6 and 16-18 years boys in West Bengal have no registered crime cases. More than 95 percent of crimes have been committed against girls in West Bengal and India. This proves that girls are more vulnerable than boys both in West Bengal as well as in India. The study reveals that as the age increases crime cases against girl’s increases in West Bengal and India. Only a few cases are recorded as crimes committed against boys in both West Bengal and India. Whereas crime cases against girls are much in number which is very shameful for our society. The result also indicates that in Indian society children are the most vulnerable and innocent victims of crime especially girls as shown in Fig 3 and 4.

Table 4: Age profile of victims of POCSO-2017

Years	Crime against children					
	West Bengal		Total	India		Total
	Boys	Girls		Boys	Girls	
6	0	63 (100.0)	63	16 (2.68)	580 (97.31)	596
6-12	06 (3.06)	190 (96.9)	196	64 (3.20)	1934 (96.79)	1998
12-16	03 (0.64)	461(99.35)	464	69 (1.10)	6203 (98.89)	6272
16-18	0	496 (100.0)	496	20 (0.25)	7839 (99.74)	7859
Total crime	9 (0.73)	1210 (99.26)	1219	169 (1.01)	16556 (98.98)	16725

Source NCRB

Table 5 and Fig 5 show offenders' relation to child victims of POCSO ACT-2017. The present study reveals that most of the crimes against children (78.4%) are committed by known persons to the victims. The highest number of crimes is committed by family friends in both West Bengal and India. In India, crime committed by online friends is much higher in percent (34.21%) than West Bengal (20.69%). Only a few crimes are committed by family members in West Bengal (7.10%) and In India (9.92%). In west Bengal, 21.5 percent of crimes are committed by people who are unknown to the victims whereas in India only 6.71 percent of crimes are committed by unknown people.

Table 5: Offenders relation to child victims of POCSO ACT-2017

Cases in which offenders were known to victim		
	WB	India
Family members	85 (7.10)	1639 (9.92)
Family friends	726 (60.65)	8116 (49.14)
Online friends	128 (10.69)	5651 (34.21)
Unknown	258 (21.55)	1109 (6.71)
Total case	1197	16515

Source NCRB

DISCUSSION

The nature and methods of committing a crime against children is changing rapidly in society. Children are victimized by sexual abuse, prostitution, physical abuse etc. of all age group, and these crimes have serious implications to children (Dijik 2016:405-425). West Bengal has contributed 2.58 percent of crimes against children in India in 2006, which increased to 4.99 percent in 2017. Share of West Bengal in overall crime against children in India is the highest in

the year 2016 (8.02 percent). This result shows that the percentage share of crimes against children in West Bengal with respect to India is increasing fast. Overall cases (registered) of crimes against children increased from 2006 to 2017 in West Bengal and India. While the overall reported cases increased 5 times in India, the cases increased 10 times in West Bengal.

Kidnapping and abduction of children is the biggest problem, in which West Bengal have 5th position among all the states of India. Number of rape cases increases until 2013, after 2013 no new rape case has been registered for the next two years. After two years, in 2016 the number of cases has increased to a record number 718. During the period 2006-2017, the number of kidnapping and abducting cases has increased 22 times in West Bengal which is alarming. Number of child murders has also increased nearly 20 times in West Bengal. In 2017 the percentage of crimes against children shows reduction in number. In India, there are still many cases of crimes, which remain unreported because of many reasons. This tendency of not reporting the crimes against children in rural areas are much higher than urban areas. It thus hides a dark side of crimes in criminal justice system as well as crime statistics (Chandrashekar 2014). Indian society is patriarchal and women and children in India largely depend on adult male member of their family for economic sustenance. Children are often the victims of sexual violence, within the family or the closest caregiver, because they depend on an adult for care, nurture, and protection. This dependency can be exploited to convince a child that a sexual relationship with a close relation is an expression of love or affection. This dependence can ensure that the child is silenced from reporting or discussing the experience with others (Inspire Handbook: Action for implementing the seven strategies for ending violence against children I-situational Analysis, 2018). Nearly one- third of all the procurement of minor girl cases in India are from West Bengal. The percentage of selling girls for prostitution has decreased over the year in India but in West Bengal 92.68 percent of cases of selling of girls for prostitution found. In the year 2017, the percentage of selling a girl for prostitution has declined declination (46.9%) in West Bengal. Both boys and girls are vulnerable to such day-to-day violence. The forms of violence they experience, the reasons why they are abused, and the impacts made on them are not always the same for boys and girls (Handbook for Ending violence against children I-situational Analysis, 2018). The study reveals that girls are more vulnerable than boys in both West Bengal and India. The study points out that more than 90 percent of the crime against children is committed by known people in India, whereas 78.4 percent of crimes are committed by known people in West Bengal.

CONCLUSIONS

This study shows that there has been an alarming increase in the crimes against children, especially in West Bengal. It is also suspected that a lot remains unreported. There should be awareness programmes by the Government of India and the respective State Governments to teach the parents and the teachers of schools about how to prepare the children against any move committed against them and how to treat the children if such mis-happenings are already

committed. The NGOs and mass medias also have their specific roles in order to stem violence against children.

Acknowledgements: Authors were thankful to National Crime Breau for proving valuable data.

Conflicts of Interest: Authors have no conflict of interest

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